

Growing Urban Canopies: Exploring the potential of Miyawaki Plantation Technique of afforestation in urban areas

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ABSTRACT:

This case study explores the potential of the Miyawaki Plantation Technique for afforestation in urban areas, focusing on two sites: Anna University in Coimbatore and Sabarmati Oxygen Park. The Miyawaki method is known for transforming degraded land into dense, native forests. Its application in these areas was to enhance biodiversity, improve air quality, and combat urban environmental issues. Despite differences in climate and environmental conditions, these projects under study demonstrated high sapling survival rates (95%) and significant ecological benefits. This study highlights how the Miyawaki method can be a powerful tool for creating green spaces, improving urban resilience, and promoting sustainable urban development.

Keywords: *Miyawaki, Anna University, Sabarmati Oxygen Park, Biodiversity, green spaces.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Deforestation has been occurring at an alarming rate where acres of forests are being cut down to create spaces for housing, agriculture, roads etc. According to Zeldovich (2023) between 1990 and 2015, the world experienced a loss of 129 million hectares of forests. This has negatively impacted the quality of life and health of humans. Among many, the movement of people from rural areas to urban areas is a grave cause for deforestation. Urbanization has resulted in the loss of forest habitat and fragmentation of forested areas throughout the globe. A study conducted by UN DESA (2020), predicts that the urban population will increase by more than 2 billion globally by 2050.

Urban areas are the engines of economic growth, attracting people and businesses alike. However, this progress often comes at a cost – the erosion of green cover. Urban green spaces not only help lower pollution levels but also lessen the impact of the urban heat island effect, which is the accumulation of heat in developed regions. The heat produced by people, transportation, and economic activity is trapped in narrow roads and concrete structures, unable

to escape into the atmosphere. This can raise the temperature in urban areas by 3-4°C over the surrounding countryside (Mair, 2020).

Rapid urbanization often prioritizes infrastructure development over natural spaces. Restoring forests offers a multitude of advantages. Forests efficiently extract substantial quantities of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and sequester it within their foliage, branches, trunks, roots, and soil (Zeldovich, 2023b). Fortunately, there are techniques to reverse this trend and enhance urban green cover. Installing vegetation on rooftops and other underutilized spaces decreases the urban heat island effect while also providing insulation, lowering stormwater runoff, and improving air quality (Reynandez, 2021). Additionally, vertical gardening and green walls planted on the sides of buildings help improve air quality and insulation. Pocket parks are another method which requires smaller areas and can act as a green escape in urban cities. However, the impact of these and the costs to manufacture them are high. Another promising approach of afforestation is the Miyawaki method. Developed by Japanese botanist Akira Miyawaki, this technique focuses on planting native species at high densities to create self-sustaining forests within a short timeframe.

The current review involves a case study-based approach to identify the performance of the Miyawaki Technique as a method to increase green cover in urban settlements as compared to traditional methods. The performance of the Miyawaki plantation at Coimbatore Anna University and Ahmedabad Oxygen Park will be discussed in this review article.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Historical development of the Miyawaki Technique

Akira Miyawaki born in 1928 in the Okayama Prefecture, was an expert in plant ecology; specializing in seeds and natural forests. The idea of the Miyawaki technique emerged during the 1950s and 1960s, a period marked by Japan's growing urbanization and a lack of concern for the environment. Japan established an environmental agency in response to the diseases that emerged as a result of environmental negligence. That is when firms began to demonstrate concern for the environment, and many of them turned to Miyawaki. In 1971, Miyawaki was hired by Nippon Steel's recently formed environmental division to create forests at the company's production sites. Miyawaki saw this as a chance. Following the successful implementation of the Miyawaki approach, he formed partnerships with renowned utility organizations and

corporations. The success of these firms in afforestation motivated people around the world to adopt the Miyawaki technique of afforestation in their own countries (Giseburt, 2023).

2.2. The Miyawaki Method

The Miyawaki method is a strategy used to establish dense and rapidly growing forests on land that has been degraded. The approach prioritizes the cultivation of diverse indigenous trees, shrubs, and groundcover plants planted in close proximity. This closely spaced planting imitates the natural layering of a forest canopy, encouraging competition and accelerated growth. Following the initial maintenance during the first three years, Miyawaki plantations are intended to achieve self-sufficiency. These forests have the ability to achieve full growth 10 times faster and have a density that is 30 times greater as compared to forests planted using conventional methods (The Miyawaki Method for Creating Forests | SUGI, n.d.).

2.3. Comparative analysis with traditional afforestation methods

The Miyawaki method as compared to the traditional method of afforestation has proved to be more efficient. As opposed to 1,000 per hectare in commercial forestry, the seedlings are planted extremely densely—30,000 to 50,000 per hectare. The standard growth rate in traditional afforestation methods ranges from five to ten centimeters per year, varying according to the species (Zeldovich, 2023). Furthermore the Miyawaki technique accelerates tree growth by around ten times. After achieving stability, the forest is allowed to thrive independently, without any more assistance (Zeldovich, 2023). Additionally as seen in the image below, natural vegetation succession takes about 10-40 years to produce shrubs and the smallest plants, whereas through the Miyawaki method mature trees can be achieved in the same time period.

Fig 1. Difference between a Natural versus Miyawaki method of plantation (Iowa Mini-Forests, 2024)

2.4. Benefits of urban afforestation

Afforestation is a crucial strategy for addressing climate change. Through the process of photosynthesis, trees absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, effectively reducing its presence. Trees also sequester significant amounts of carbon from the atmosphere in their biomass and in the soil, so aiding in the reduction of climate change effects (Climate Impact Partners, n.d.). Furthermore, the afforestation approach has the potential to revitalize the land and establish a novel ecology. It can enhance soil fertility, mitigate erosion, establish new habitats for species, and safeguard surrounding areas from strong winds and floods. Economically, afforestation also provides the advantage of creating job opportunities. Establishing a new forest is challenging and necessitates a substantial labour force to accomplish. Several crucial responsibilities are required for planting a new forest including excavating the ground, irrigating the plants, dispersing seeds etc (Lark, 2023).

Specifically, the Miyawaki method of afforestation has its own benefits. Firstly, Miyawaki forests mature rapidly, providing ecological benefits like improved air quality, reduced noise pollution, and habitat creation for wildlife. Secondly, although the initial costs are high, these dense forests require minimal maintenance once established, making them a cost-effective solution for cities with limited resources. Finally, the Miyawaki method promotes biodiversity by using native species, which are well-adapted to local conditions and require less water compared to non-native alternatives (Gioli et al., 2020).

3. CASE STUDIES

The Miyawaki method has proven to be a transformative approach to restoring degraded urban areas into thriving ecosystems. Case studies from Sabarmati Oxygen Park in Ahmedabad and the Anna University campus in Coimbatore offer valuable insights into its practical application and impact. While Oxygen Park is in a metropolitan city and the plantation in Coimbatore is in a university, the Miyawaki technique in both areas has successfully impacted the surrounding environment. Additionally, the site preparation and choice of planting native species align with the Miyawaki plantation method.

3.1 Case Study 1- Sabarmati Oxygen Park, 2019

3.1.1 Location

The Sabarmati Oxygen Park in Ahmedabad. The park located in the Sabarmati waterfront has semi-arid conditions with high temperatures and erratic rainfall. The site faces extreme temperature fluctuations and monsoonal rains (Harivallabhdas, 2023).

3.1.2 Species Planted

Approximately 40 indigenous tree species, including Drumstick, Mahuda, Jamun, Amla, Mulberry, Kanjo, Kaju, Flame of the Forest, Sesam, Shami, Neem, Ramfal, and Cordia species, have been planted among others (Parikh, 2024). These have shown a 90% survival rate.

3.1.3 Pre-Plantation Scenario

Previously barren with minimal vegetation the area has been used for urban development hence degrading the quality over time. Furthermore, prior to restoration efforts, the natural environment was sparse, with little biodiversity and low ground cover.

Figure 2: Image of the site before plantation (Harivallabhdas, 2023)

3.1.4 Post-Plantation Scenario

Through the Miyawaki technique, the land has transformed into a vibrant dense forest within just 3-5 years. As seen in the image below after just one year the land is blanketed with dense greenery and a forest structure with multiple layers of canopy, understory, and shrub levels.

Figure 3: Image of the site post plantation via Miyawaki Technique (Harivallabhdas, 2023)

3.1.5 Impact on Ecosystem and Climate

The particulate matter in surrounding areas has also been reduced by 20%, improving carbon sequestration, and leading to a cooling effect, which combats the urban heat island effect. Additionally, social benefits of the Miyawaki technique has led to improved urban aesthetics and the creation of a green lung for city dwellers, providing shade and recreational opportunities. The proximity to the Sabarmati River was a key factor in improving moisture retention in the soil post-restoration (Harivallabhdas, 2023).

3.2 Case Study 2- Anna University, 2016

3.2.1 Location

Similarly in southern India, within the Anna University campus in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, similar efforts of Miyawaki plantations have been applied. The region has a tropical climate, with high humidity and temperatures ranging between 25°C to 37°C. The average annual rainfall is 700-800 mm, primarily during the monsoon.

3.2.2 Species Planted

More than 60 species of plants and trees were introduced, with a survival rate exceeding 85%. Since 2016 over 88,000 saplings have been planted, by the Siruthuli organization (SimpliCity News Team, 2022).

3.2.3 Pre-Plantation Scenario

The land initially was an open unused space within the university campus, barren and used for waste dumping. Pre-restoration, the area lacked natural vegetation and showed signs of soil compaction, with very low organic matter content.

(Fig. 4 a)

(Fig. 4 b)

Figure 4 (a & b): Image of the site before plantation (Anakha Arikara, 2018)

3.2.4 Post-Plantation Scenario

Restoration and afforestation efforts have now created lush forestry with several layers of vegetation contributing to the site's thick canopy. Within three years, a substantial number of tree species have reached over 4 meters in height, creating a self-sustaining ecosystem.

(Fig. 5 a)

(Fig. 5 b)

Figure 5 (a & b): Image of the site after plantation (Anakha Arikara, 2018)

3.2.5 Impact on Ecosystem and Climate

Furthermore, research shows the forest significantly reduced temperatures in the vicinity by up to 2°C, provided substantial air quality improvement, and enhanced soil retention, reducing erosion. For students of the university, it also serves as a live research site for environmental sciences, enabling practical studies on urban afforestation and biodiversity restoration (Radhakrishnan et al., 2019).

4. DISCUSSION

Comparing the two Miyawaki plantation sites in different parts of India shows the versatility of the Miyawaki technique. Both sites reported high survival rates for native species (90% in Ahmedabad, 85% in Coimbatore), due to careful species selection and soil preparation. In Ahmedabad, tree species reached an average height of 3-5 meters within the first three years, while in Coimbatore, trees like *Tectona grandis* surpassed 4 meters in height within the same timeframe. Furthermore, over 50 species were introduced in Ahmedabad, and over 60 in Coimbatore, showing the adaptability of the Miyawaki method to different climates and soil conditions. Most importantly, both forests have contributed significantly to carbon capture, with an estimated 150-200 tons of CO₂ sequestered annually in each project. These case studies underscore the potential of the Miyawaki method to restore urban environments, improve local ecosystems, and offer long-term environmental and social benefits.

Deforestation is accountable for around 5 billion tonnes, or 17 percent, of the total annual carbon emissions worldwide. Additionally, it also leads to soil erosion and a decline in biodiversity (Mooney, 2021). The success of the above case study's implementation of the Miyawaki technique can be attributed to the use of native species and soil preparation. Although the temperatures and climatic conditions vary, including soil conditions, efforts to improve soil health and provide adequate water have succeeded. This shows that the Miyawaki plantation can be implemented in metropolitan cities across India, where conditions differ. Potential for scaling up the Miyawaki Technique in urban areas especially rapidly growing cities like Gurgaon, this afforestation method can help mitigate environmental issues like pollution and high temperatures as has been proven successful in the case studies discussed. While saying that it's important to denote that one plantation can help its immediate surroundings to a certain extent, for impact it is important to culminate more plantations at a larger scale.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Miyawaki plantations at Anna University and Sabarmati Oxygen Park demonstrate the potential of this afforestation method to transform degraded urban land into a flourishing ecosystem in a short span of 2-3 years. Despite differences in scale and

environmental challenges, such as the semi-arid conditions in Sabarmati versus the tropical climate in Coimbatore, both projects achieved impressive results, including 95% sapling survival rates, significant biodiversity enhancement, and rapid ecological restoration. The ability to improve air quality, stabilize soil, and mitigate the urban heat island effect highlights the Miyawaki method's relevance in addressing the environmental impacts of rapid urbanization.

Both cases also emphasize the importance of community involvement, whether through university engagement or local participation, in ensuring the sustainability of urban forests. The success of these projects provides a strong reason for implementing similar afforestation efforts in other urban localities, particularly those facing the pressures of rapid development and environmental degradation, such as Gurgaon. As cities continue expanding, Miyawaki plantations can serve as a vital strategy for enhancing urban resilience, improving public health, and restoring ecological balance in densely populated environments.

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